

THE CONCEPT OF REWRITING, TYPES AND ITS DISPLAYS IN THE DIGITAL JOURNALISM

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ABSTRACT: *This article discusses the concept of rewriting, its types, distinctive features, its place in digital journalism today and how it ranks in the competition in the field of journalism.*

Key words: *digital journalism, rewriting, copywriting, Internet, competition*

INTRODUCTION

Journalism as a kind of activity involves the collection and processing of information, therefore, journalists, to one degree or another, have always relied on other people's texts (both journalistic and non-journalistic) when preparing their own materials. However, only with the advent of the internet and its use in the work of journalists, the processing of texts took on an unprecedented scale, giving rise to a qualitatively new phenomenon in journalism - rewriting.

METHODS

Rewriting (from the Eng. Rewrite) is a rewriting of any source text in order to obtain a unique text that is identical in meaning to the original. Of course, the rewritten text is unique only from the point of view of search engines (Яндекс, Google) and computer programs (for example, Advego Plagiatus shows the degree of uniqueness of the text, the sources of the text, the percentage of coincidence), while a person can easily notice the semantic similarity of the rewritten text with the original. Specialists in lexical change of texts are called rewriters. The concepts of copywriting and rewriting are similar, but they have differences. Rewriting is the creation of a new and unique article based on several texts. The author must remake the original text, without departing from the theme of the source, making it unique. When rewriting, the authors use various techniques.¹

Synonymizing - This is an easy way to rewrite an article. The author needs to find synonyms for individual words without changing the structure of phrases. Can be manual or automatic.

¹ <https://ocean-agency.com.ua/chto-takoe-kopiraiting-reraiting-posting-neiming>

Text reduction - words that do not entail changes in the meaning of the article are removed from the source.

Partial editing - changing a small part of the text without changing the meaning. Relevant when working with large texts.

Classical edition - the sentence is rewritten in its own words, without losing its meaning.

Deep rewriting - when rewriting, the author takes as a basis not only the basic data, but also uses additional sources.

Rewriting is ordered in the case when you need to save the budget. Such texts are cheaper than copyright materials. It is important to remember that the line between rewriting and copywriting is very thin. In rewriting, all unnecessary facts are removed from the source text, if necessary, the style of presentation, the scheme for presenting information, the volume are changed, and any necessary elements are added. As a result of the work of the rewriter, an absolutely unique text should be obtained. There are special programs for determining the uniqueness of rewrites. The highest quality rewrite has 100% uniqueness, but it is possible to reduce this level to 90-95%. The resulting article after rewriting should not contain:

- factual errors;
- fictions and conjectures of the rewriter;
- rewriter's comments;
- personal opinion of the rewriter;
- something that is not in the source text.

A high-quality rewrite will be no different from copyright, that is, from the original article.¹ The rewriter rewrites the original articles in order to get articles that differ from each other. The text can be recycled once, or two or three, or even more. Sometimes it happens that the customer asks to rework the article more than a dozen times, and each time in a different way, in order to get different copies, which will then be published on different sites. In other words, the rewriter does not create texts, but only uses the available information. In traditional media, many of the techniques used in rewriting and copywriting, due to technical features, simply will not work. There are sites on the Internet that host offers from employers to freelancers who rewrite texts (for example: free-lance.ru, freelance.ru, freelancejob.ru, weblancer.net, etc.). There are also "supermarkets" of unique content, such as textsale.ru and advego.ru, where anyone can buy cheap text on any topic without an author's signature with the right to put their name under it or not put it at all. Most often, on such sites you can buy advertising texts necessary to fill the content of online stores, company websites, etc. But these sites also have texts that can rightfully be called journalistic. Today, some

¹ Изв. Саратовского университета. Нов. сер. Сер. Филология. Журналистика. 2014. Т. 14, вып. 1 В. Костенко, Копирайтинг и рерайтинг в сетевых СМИ –новые виды журналистики?

media outlets are actively buying “rewired” plagiarism from authors, and not only second-rate specialized print and online media, but also very popular publications live on such texts.

RESULTS

Indeed, the current state of affairs is as follows: for many media, the Internet has become a self-sufficient source of information, and if you call a spade a spade, it has significantly expanded the possibilities of plagiarism. “Previously, compilation and abstracting required hours and days of picking in libraries, now it takes several keystrokes,” says Andrey Miroshnichenko, author of books on mass communications, editor-in-chief of the “Банковское обозрение” magazine. “Technological simplicity creates temptations. events - and we will see that the flow is statistically unstoppable.”¹

Conventionally, there are three options for using other people’s materials: copy-pasting, rewriting and copyright. The term “copy-pasting”, formed by a combination of words-copy (copy) and paste (paste), respectively, means a frontal reprint of the text without any changes for the sake of external unrecognizability. Rewriting - rewriting the source text in other words, but copyright - compiling material from different sources. It is very difficult to estimate exactly how much of everything published is a secondary product. Of course, this depends on the market segment, as well as the level of sites or media, however, according to Andrey Shipilov, editor-in-chief of the online magazine Reclamun.ru, in general, primary content on the Internet is a fraction of a percent (in print media - no more than 25%). That is, the Internet is filled with content that Shipilov calls pink noise.²

In addition, the collection and copying of content, primarily news, has long been automated. This mechanism for automatically broadcasting media materials to other sites is called RSS (Really Simple Syndication). A special program visits source sites or simply searches for keywords, then copies pieces of text and publishes material on the required resource. It happens that robots even do machine rewriting (as a rule, they replace words with synonyms), and before publication, a person views the text received by the rewriter robot.

DISCUSSION

Today, we can conditionally distinguish three options for using other people’s materials: copy-pasting, rewriting (rewriting) and copyright. There are two types of rewriting that are fundamentally different from each other: mechanical (useless) and adapted (useful).

Rewriting of the first type is designed to hide the weakness of the media in the search for information, the lack of correspondents, it is necessary in view of the requirement to observe the frequency in the release of fresh texts. A vivid example of

¹ Боярский А. Пустота хуже воровства // Коммерсант — Деньги. 2010. № 9. С. 43–47.

² Боярский А. Пустота хуже воровства // Коммерсант — Деньги. 2010. № 9. С. 43–47.

such rewriting is the news of online publications that rewrite texts from each other in order, first of all, to fill in news feeds and adapt texts for automatic news aggregators (like Yandex.News); at the same time, the latter should perceive the texts as unique and highlight them in the topic of the day, providing traffic to Internet publications and, as a result, an increase in advertising revenue. Moreover, in the texts rewritten in this way, there may or may not be links to the original source (which, in fact, some media are struggling with, as mentioned above).

The second type of rewriting is what is usually called an adaptation, a popular exposition. Everything superfluous is thrown out of the text, the wording is made less bureaucratic and “dry”, reading the rewritten text is greatly simplified. Sometimes rewriting the text makes it much more understandable to an unprepared reader, especially if the article is “sharpened” for a specific target audience (youth, the elderly, the reader of an entertainment publication, etc.).

When promoting sites, rewriting is resorted to in the following cases:

- need to optimize the existing text;
- creating content when promoting articles;
- changing the style of an existing text;
- filling product cards when promoting online stores;
- maintenance of the news section;
- uniqueness of technical characteristics;
- need a large amount of unique texts in a short time.¹

Rewriting of the second type is invaluable in the popular science press or in materials about science in non-specialized Internet publications and mass media intended for a wide audience. The fact is that the popularization of science is built precisely on rewrite of the second type, since popularizing journalists deliberately “translate” specialized knowledge into the language of an unprepared reader, turning boring scientific information into an interesting and understandable readership. The job of the science journalist is precisely to process specific and often jargon-laden information into a form that the average media consumer can understand and appreciate. To verify this, you can at least look at news articles in online publications and the popular science press, in the preparation of which journalists take information from the websites of scientific institutions and from scientific articles, and then simplify it.²

¹ <https://uniofweb.ru/wiki/rewriting/>

² Вестник СПбГУ. Сер. 9. 2012. Вып. 1, А. С. Колоев РЕРАЙТ КАК НОВОЕ ЯВЛЕНИЕ В СОВРЕМЕННОЙ ЖУРНАЛИСТИКЕ

CONCLUSION

Thus, thanks to the advent of the internet, the collection of information was greatly simplified, and journalists began to abuse the opportunity. And although rewriting is sometimes imperceptible and often not a violation of copyright, its use is most often perceived as a low level of professionalism of journalists. However, one should not forget that in some cases (for example, when popularizing science in the media), rewriting plays a positive role.

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